

INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION IN TEACHING STUDENTS ON COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *The given article explores the skills of using interactive methods in teaching computer science and information technology to students and explores interdisciplinary integration.*

Keywords: *computer science and information technologies, "dual tree" method, integration, information culture, professional pedagogy, interactive methods.*

Introduction

It is important to suggest that teaching informatics and information technologies to school students is crucial in the globe nowadays. This field not only involves acquiring technical knowledge but also provides students with various skills necessary to succeed in the modern world.

In the Concept for the Development of Teaching Informatics and Information Technologies in the Preschool, General Secondary, Vocational, and Higher Education Systems of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Informatics is considered a core subject in general education.

Taking into account the national characteristics and the ongoing reforms in the country, the goal is to align the teaching of Informatics with international standards to prepare qualified personnel for the global market. This is being achieved through the development and implementation of normative documents for Informatics education, including state educational standards (SES), qualification requirements, curricula, and syllabi.

In countries with highly industrialized production processes such as the United Kingdom, France, Germany, the United States, Israel, South Korea, China, and other developed nations, Informatics is a core subject in general education. Specifically, South Korea, being one of the world's most advanced countries in terms of informatization and computerization, has established modern traditions for teaching Informatics in schools.

In our country, special attention is being paid to the integration of information technologies into the educational process.

Main part

In general secondary education schools, attention should be given to improving the quality of teaching Informatics and Information Technologies and to using interactive methods in organizing the teaching process. Furthermore, there is a need to improve the methodology for shaping students' knowledge in Informatics and Information Technologies and to conduct scientific research on how to use these methods effectively in teaching the subject.

Definitely, the effectiveness of the educational process can be increased through various approaches. Innovative approaches are essential for modernizing the education system and achieving educational efficiency.

Certainly, given the relevance of these tasks, this research discusses the use of interactive methods in teaching Informatics and Information Technologies, analyzes their current state, and develops effective usage methodologies and corresponding methodological recommendations.

Purpose of the Research:

The purpose of this research is to analyze the possibilities of using interactive methods in shaping students' knowledge in Informatics and Information Technologies, as well as to examine interdisciplinary integration, identify its effective aspects, and study how these methods are used in the educational process.

Tasks of the Research:

To identify the potential for using interactive methods in teaching Informatics and Information Technologies.

The current task of school education is for teachers to effectively utilize new innovative information technologies during lessons, ensuring that students receive information in a clear and understandable way. Therefore, it is essential for teachers to organize and teach lessons using modern innovative information technologies to help students understand and study the subject of Informatics clearly and precisely.

In order to increase students interest in the subject, unconventional and engaging methods, such as role-playing games and modern interactive methods, should be employed to enhance lesson effectiveness. In this regard, the use of the "Double Tree" method in teaching has proven to be highly effective.

Besides that, this method is appropriate for reinforcing the knowledge gained during a theoretical lesson. To implement this, the teacher first draws a "double tree" diagram. For saving time during the lesson, the tree diagrams can be pre-drawn. Students then write the relevant information related to the topic on both sides of the tree.

In general, secondary education schools, one of the sections in teaching Informatics and Information Technologies is working with MS Excel. Students are required to solve certain problems using MS Excel.

Now, let's consider using the "Double Tree" method in teaching the topic "Working with Functions in Excel" on Informatics and Information Technologies. The assignment topic could be: "Graphs of Functions in Excel."

- Excel Menu Section
- Graphs in Excel

In this example, the "Double Tree" method can be applied by drawing a tree diagram, where on one side, students can list the functions and formulas used in Excel (such as SUM, AVERAGE) and on the other side, they can draw or describe how these functions are visualized through graphs in Excel.

This method will help students to reinforce their understanding of both the theoretical and practical aspects of working with functions and graphs in Excel.

Questions and Answers

"Double Tree" method.

Step 1: In this task, students will make a presentation.

Step 2: In the second task, students will write questions on one side of a tree and answers on the other side based on the given topic.

Using this method, students can attempt to find the answers to the following questions:

What commands are included in the menu of the Excel?

What mathematical functions are used in Excel?

What types of charts can be created in Excel?

How are graphs of elementary functions in mathematics created?

As a result, students will study the answers to the questions while thinking freely.

While teaching the subject of Informatics and Information Technologies at schools, the following aspects are important in developing students' motivation to learn the subject using interactive methods in the process of mastering the topics:

Creating an environment that ensures students success during their activities, focusing on the complexity of the tasks given to them and, of course, evaluating the results;

Setting problems to increase students' interest, using all the opportunities of the learning material to activate independent thinking;

Encouraging collaboration among students in the lesson, organizing mutual help, and establishing a positive attitude in the process of mastering the topic as a whole.

Moreover, in teaching the subjects Informatics and Information Technologies, the main focus should be on developing practical skills for school students. It is also important to teach students how to use software tools effectively and safely, preparing them to solve real-life problems.

In practical exercises on "Working with functions in Excel," it was found to be effective to organize intrasubject integration with other school subjects. For example, considering the knowledge gained in algebra, the following example could be given in practical assignments: "Plot the graphs of elementary mathematical functions in one coordinate system and determine at which values of x one function's value is greater or smaller than another."

$$y = 2x^2$$

$$y = x^2 - 3$$

$$y = 1 - 3x$$

Students can create graphs of these functions in Excel in different colors within the same coordinate system.

Figure 2: Graphs of Functions in Excel

Students can determine the value of which function is greater or smaller than another by referring to the table of values of the functions calculated in Excel (Figure 2).

In practical and laboratory sessions, the knowledge learned in theoretical classes can be further enhanced. Practical and laboratory sessions are key elements of an innovative lesson, as they develop students' creativity, thinking abilities, and personal potential, as well as provide psychological knowledge. Therefore, increasing attention to organizing practical and laboratory sessions and structuring them as innovative lessons is a key issue.

Surprisingly, at present time it is essential for all students to have sufficient knowledge of information technologies, which should be the main criterion. For this reason, organizing the teaching of Informatics and Information Technologies at an innovative lesson level leads to effective results, not only in fostering students' interest in the subject but also in developing their knowledge and skills.

In conclusion, it should be suggested that using interactive methods in the educational process helps to shape students' motivations for creative thinking and the application of acquired knowledge and skills, as well as their interest in the subject. Organizing lessons based on interdisciplinary integration allows students to effectively assimilate knowledge while deeply understanding the continuity of general education subjects. Thus, the subject of Informatics and Information Technologies can be taught in a more engaging and effective way.

REFERENCES

1. Karimov Q.M., Omonova S.M. "Using the internet in teaching students knowledge about Informatics and Information Technologies." *International Scientific and Practical Journal "Economics and Society"*, N. 2(117)-1, 2024, Pp. 359-364.

2. Karimov K.M. "Use of interactive methods in teaching via computer networks." Innovative and Technological Development of Science and Education in the 21st Century. International Scientific and Practical Conference, Moscow, July 31, 2020, pages 33-35.
3. Karimov Q.M. Methodology of Teaching Informatics. Educational Manual, T.: "Fan va Ta'lim" Publishing, 2022, 242 pages.
4. Karimov Q.M., Karimova SH.Q. "Increasing student activity in distance learning." Prospects for improving the technical, software, and methodological support for the introduction of distance education in Higher Education Systems. Collection of materials from the Republican Scientific-Practical Conference, Karshi, May 28, 2021, Pp. 16-17.
5. Karimov Q.M., Karimova Sh.K. "Using Graphic Organizers in teaching Informatics." Modern Problems and Solutions on Information and Communication Technologies and Telecommunications. Collection of reports from the Republican Scientific and Technical Forum, Part 2, Fergana, May 30-31, 2019, Pp. 483-485.
6. Karimov K.M. "Using the Step-by-Step Method to Teach Students to Work with Diagrams." Pedagogy: Scientific-Theoretical and Methodological Journal, N. 04/2024, T.: 2024, Pp. 94-97.